

Removal of lead using non-living biomass of blue green algae Species in aqueous solutions

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Abstract : Contamination of soil and water with heavy metals is of great concern with regard to environmental pollution. Lead (Pb) is one of the heavy metals which is highly toxic and causes health hazards to the living beings even at very low concentrations. It is used as an industrial raw material for storage battery manufacturing, printing, pigments, fuels, photographic materials and explosive manufacturing etc. Removal of Pb from environmental matrices was studied using physical adsorbents like active carbon and charcoal¹. But bio-sorption has an advantage in that it is cost effective and does not cause secondary pollution.

Batch equilibrium sorption experiments were carried out for the adsorption of lead using blue green algae Sp. harvested from Nacharam Lake, Hyderabad. Standard samples of Pb in concentrations of 56, 28 and 14 ppm were taken and bio-sorption experiments were carried out. Time of contact, pH and quantity of biomass were optimized for obtaining maximum bio-sorption. Results showed that 94.28% removal of Pb was observed at 14 ppm concentration with mixed species of blue green algae. Bio-sorption of Pb onto algal bio-sorbents occurred rapidly. Most of the metal was bound to the adsorbent within 30 min of contact. Optimum biomass concentration was found to be 1.66 g/100 ml at pH of 6.5. Regeneration experiments were carried out to understand the sustainability of the adsorbent.

Reuse of the used biomass was done repeatedly to understand the efficiency of the adsorbent. It was noticed that the adsorbent can be reused with the same efficiency at least for 3 times. The method developed was found to be fast and efficient for removal of Pb from water solutions.

Keywords : Blue green algae, adsorption, lead, bio-sorption.

Introduction

The presence of heavy metals in aquatic environment is known to cause severe damage to aquatic life. Most of heavy metals are soluble in water and form aqueous solutions and consequently cannot be separated by ordinary physical and chemical means of separation. Many physico-chemical methods using granular activated carbon², heartwood charcoal of *Areca catechu*³ and different types of clays⁴ were reported in the literature, but physical adsorbents have the disadvantage of causing secondary pollution and quite often they are not cost effective. In this context, bio-sorbents can be used as absorption materials for heavy metals which are cheap and available abundantly. Bio-sorption technique was investigated as an alternative method for treating the metal-containing water of low concentrations. In response to heavy metals, micro-organisms have evolved various measures via pro-

cesses such as transport across the cell membrane, bio-sorption to cell walls and entrapment in extra cellular capsules, precipitation, and complexation and oxidation-reduction reactions. Algae, a specific group of organism, possess high metal binding capacity and the cell wall plays an important role in metal ion binding. This is due the presence of carboxyl, hydroxyl, sulphate and amino groups in the algal cell wall polysaccharides, which can act as binding sites for metals. Bio-sorption of Pb using brown algae⁵, apple pomace⁶, spirogyra⁷, yeast⁸, fungi⁹ and spirulina¹⁰ was studied extensively. But so far, no report is available on the adsorption of lead using blue green algae. In the present study the adsorption of Pb using blue green algae from water solutions in trace levels was investigated and the results obtained are presented and discussed.

Material and methods :**Preparation of biomass :**

Bio-sorption of Pb from aqueous solutions using dead biomass of blue green algae collected from Nacharam Lake, near IICT, Hyderabad. Bio-mass was prepared from blue green algae samples and chloroform was added. It was kept for sonication for 30 min. The algae sample was then kept for shaking in an orbital shaker. The supernatant was separated after six hours and the powder was dried and used for bio-sorption experiments.

Preparation of standard solution :

Pb standard solution of 1000 ppm was prepared by weighing appropriate amount of lead nitrate and diluting it to 1000 ml. Batch sorption experiments were carried out in 250 ml conical flasks. The flasks were placed on shaker incubator with constant shaking at 120 rpm and temperature around 30 °C. After separation of used biosorbent by centrifugation, the residual concentration of Pb was analyzed using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). The solution was diluted to prepare Pb solutions of 56, 28 and 14 ppm.

Optimization of contact time :

Optimum contact time of the bio-sorbent for maximum adsorption was determined by carrying out experiments, keeping quantity of biomass and pH constant. The treatment efficiency was measured at different times of contact by AAS. The experiments were carried out for 7 h and samples were drawn periodically for analysis.

Optimization of pH :

Experiments were carried out for determining the pH by keeping the quantity of biomass and time of contact constant. The pH was varied from 6 to 8.5.

Optimization of biomass :

Experiments were carried out to optimize the quantity of biomass by keeping the pH and contact time constant. The quantity of biomass was varied between 0.5–3.0 g for 150 ml of test solution.

Instrumentation :

Heavy metal content in all the solutions was quantified using AAS (Perkin-Elmer-GBC 932 AA). The amount of metal sorbed was calculated from the difference in metal concentration in the aqueous phase before and after adsorption.

Results and discussions

Contact time of biomass with the test solution, pH and quantity of biomass are three principal parameters which determine the degree of adsorption of Pb to the biomass. Therefore experiments were carried out to determine the optimum contact time, pH and quantity of biomass to achieve efficiency.

Optimization of time :

Fig. 1 shows the adsorption of Pb to the dead blue green algae species as a function of contact time. It was observed that at 30 min time of contact the remaining concentration of Pb in the solution reduced from 100 ppm to 1.4 ppm. The experiments carried out up to 400 min. A small quantity of solution taken out periodically for determining the concentration of Pb in the solution. It was observed that the concentration of remaining solution increased continuously up to 400 min. Therefore it is concluded that 30 min was the optimum contact time of adsorption for maximum adsorption of Pb to the bio-sorbent.

Fig. 1. Optimization of contact time for bio-sorption of Pb to dead blue green algae.

Optimization of pH :

The pH of the solution influences both metal binding sites on the cell surface and the chemistry of metal solution¹¹. In order to understand the effect of pH on the degree of bio-sorption, uptake of Pb^{II} ions onto dead algae as function of pH was studied in the pH range of 6.0–8.5. The time of contact was kept 30 min and the biomass quantity was kept constant (1.5 g) pH was varied from 6.0 to 8.5. Fig. 2 shows the effect of pH on Pb bio-sorption. The bio-sorption observed was maximum at pH 6.5.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on Pb bio-sorption using dead biomass of blue green algae (initial Pb^{II} conc. 100 mg/L, temperature 28–35 °C, biomass 1.00 g/L).

Optimization of the quantity of biomass :

The dependence of Pb bio-sorption was studied at room temperature by varying the adsorbent amount from 1.0 g to 3.0 while keeping pH (6.5), and contact time (30 min) constant. Fig. 3 shows the effect of the quantity of biomass on Pb bio-sorption. It is noticed that 2.5 g of biomass per 150 ml of Pb solution was optimum for achieving maximum efficiency.

Fig. 3. Effect of quantity of the bio-sorbent on Pb bio-sorption (initial Pb conc. 100 mg/L and at pH 6.5).

Pb bio-sorption at optimized experimental conditions viz. 30 min contact time, 6.5 pH and 2.5 g of biomass per 150 ml solution were used and experiments were carried out with 56, 28 and 14 ppm Pb solutions. The results obtained are presented in Fig. 4. It is observed that the maximum reduction of Pb (94.28%) was observed at 14 ppm concentration of Pb under optimized conditions. At

Fig. 4. Bio-sorption at different concentrations of Pb under optimized conditions (biomass 2.5 g/L, time 30 min and at pH 6.5).

56 ppm, 87.5% removal of Pb was observed and at 28 ppm, 90% reduction was observed.

Reuse of biomass :

Reuse of biomass was carried out at 100 ppm under optimized conditions. It was found that the biomass can be reused with almost same efficiency 3 times. Fig. 5 shows the results of reuse of the biomass.

Fig. 5. Effect of reuse of the blue green algae on Pb bio-sorption at 100 ppm under optimized conditions (biomass 2.5 g/L, time 30 min and at pH 6.5).

Reuse of biomass was carried out at all concentrations of Pb 6 times. It was found that the biomass can be reused with almost same efficiency 3 times. Fig. 6 shows the results of reuse of the biomass.

Regeneration of biomass :

Regeneration of the adsorbent was studied. After regeneration of the bio-sorbent, experiments were carried

Fig. 6. Effect of reuse of the blue green algae on Pb bio-sorption at 100 ppm under optimized conditions (biomass 2.5 g/L, time 30 min and at pH 6.5).

out to understand the efficiency of the bio-sorbent, the efficiency was found to be very good.

Conclusions

Dead biomass of blue green algae Sp. could be used as an efficient bio-sorbent material for the removal of Pb ions from aqueous solutions. Removal of Pb 94.28% was achieved at 14 ppm concentration. Blue green algae was reported for the first time for bio-sorption of Pb from aqueous solution. The percentage of adsorption achieved is higher than the reports available in the literature.

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